

INTRODUCING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES TO STUDENTS AT THE PRIMARY LEVEL OF EDUCATION.

Raimova Zulfiya Almirzaevna.

Denov Institute of entrepreneurship and pedagogy

Scientific supervisor. Uralova Aysuluv Poyonovna Termez State University

***Abstract:** The methods used by different schools of speech analysis are very different. In particular, the analysis of everyday dialogue and works of Chafe is based on natural speech materials. At the same time, in the analysis of everyday dialogue, generalizations are obtained by identifying recurring, dominant patterns, and Chaf prefers the method of introspection. In Tomlin's works, the empirical material consists of experimental rather than natural data, and the processing of the material involves the standard use of statistical tests for cognitive psychology.*

***Key words:** Educational level, education, modern requirements, primary school, national curriculum.*

In recent years, decrees and decisions have been adopted on the organization of all stages of education based on modern requirements, and based on this, changes have been made to the basis of almost all programs and textbooks. The biggest reason for this was the fact that our national curriculum could not match the international requirements and the results of outstanding educational processes abroad. A special range of methodological issues is related to the transcription of oral speech. Any attempt to objectively record (transcribe) spoken language forces us to solve many complex interpretive and technical problems unknown to linguists who study only written texts. Discourse experts have long understood that not only words are important in correcting spoken discourse, but also many other situations—pauses, prosody, laughter, repeating words, full-bo non-words, etc. Without these details, a meaningful analysis of speech is simply not possible.

By providing students with digital technologies at the initial stage of education, creating opportunities for mastering digital skills, developing analytical and critical thinking, educating young people in the conditions of large-scale digital transformation that will be necessary in the future and imparting skills.

An important factor in the development of digital literacy of students is the purposeful and effective use of digital technologies by teachers in education, increasing the need for an individual approach, and the implementation of digital knowledge and skills. That said, the development of consistent transcription methods and the choice of a reasonable level of detail are very difficult issues. Therefore, at present, the principles of transcription of spoken speech are the subject of almost the entire scientific field (E.A. Zemskaya group, J. Dubois and his co-authors J. Gampers, etc.). Another important methodological innovation in recent years is the increasingly active use of text corpora in speech analysis. There are a number of computer jobs in the world with millions of targets that can be used to test the hypotheses put forward. Most of these corpora are related to English, but there are also corpora for some other languages¹. After the educational reforms, we can see that our National Curriculum compared with the International Curriculum has a significant shift in the curriculum. Taking textbooks from old programs as an example, the previous textbooks were written in difficult academic language that made the students bored and not understand the subject. But today, education is based on global learning outcomes. That is, if the student could not learn a topic in the textbook, in the program, he will study that topic again.

It was not divided into hours like before. Whether the student learns or not, he moves on to the next one. As a result, the child began to hate the lesson as he did not understand. His self-esteem would decrease. That was the biggest problem. Now it's not just about memorizing, but about encouraging students to be ready for tomorrow's life. That is, if he can express his critical opinion in the classroom, think creatively, learn to work as a team, find a solution to a problem, make the right decision, put forward a new idea, and change the world from the point of view of science. visual perception skills are formed. All programs and textbooks have been revised in recent years to address these issues².

One such textbook is the textbook "Mother language and reading literacy" for primary grades. reading literacy is the basis for success not only in the educational system, but also in other areas. Mainly international programs PISA, PIRLS. Programs

and textbooks that meet the requirements of studies such as TIMSS and TAILS and are based on them

was created. It is shown that mathematics is the essence of human life from the elementary grades. Mathematics is the science of quantitative relationships and spatial forms of the real world.

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